

Development and validation of HPTLC method for simultaneous analysis of Tramadol HCl and paracetamol in fixed-dose combination tablets

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Abstract : This paper presents the development and validation of an improved method for the simultaneous analysis of Tramadol HCl (TMD) and paracetamol (PAR) using high-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC) with densitometric detection. Separation was performed on silica gel 60F₂₅₄ plates. The mobile phase is comprised of chloroform, methanol and ethyl acetate (7.5 : 1.5 : 0.5, v : v : v). The detection wavelength was 254 nm. The *R_f* values of TMD and PAR were found to be 0.2 ± 0.03 and 0.4 ± 0.04, respectively. An F-test indicated that calibration graphs were adequately linear at the evaluated concentration ranges. The pooled %RSD for repeatability of the percentage amount recovered for TMD and PAR were found to be 0.73 and 0.49, and the pooled %RSD for time-different intermediate precision were 1.72 and 1.21 respectively. The percentage recoveries for the trueness were 98.6% ± 1.5 for TMD and 99.3% ± 1.7 for PAR (n = 3). The developed HPTLC method was found to be new, accurate, sensitive, precise and was successfully used to analyze fixed-dose tablets samples of TMD and PAR.

Keywords : Tramadol HCl, paracetamol, simultaneous estimation, HPTLC.

Introduction

Tramadol HCl (TMD), (+/-) *cis*-2-((dimethylamino)-methyl)-1-(3-methoxyphenyl)cyclohexanol hydrochloride (Fig. 1) is a centrally acting analgesic, having agonist actions at the μ -opioid receptor and affects reuptake at the noradrenergic and serotonergic systems. Tramadol is a compound with mild and delayed μ -agonist activity¹. Paracetamol (PAR), *N*-(4-hydroxyphenyl)ethanamide (Fig. 2) is a widely used analgesic and antipyretic for the relief of fever, headaches, and other minor aches and pains, and is a major ingredient in numerous cold and flu rem-

Fig. 1. Structure of Tramadol HCl.

Fig. 2. Structure of paracetamol.

edies. In combination with nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and opioid analgesics, paracetamol is used also in the management of severe pain (such as postoperative pain)².

Literature survey revealed that various analytical methods like spectrophotometric³⁻⁶, HPLC⁶⁻¹⁴, GC¹⁵ and HPTLC¹⁶⁻¹⁹ have been reported for the determination of Tramadol HCl and paracetamol either individually or combination with some other drugs. Tramadol HCl and paracetamol are available in combined dosage forms. Most methods reported in the literature for the simultaneous

determination of TMD and PAR in formulations by using HPLC. However, there is lack of such equipment in many resource limited countries. In poor countries, where such equipment is available, the high costs of HPLC grade solvents and columns and the lack of the possibility to analyze many samples simultaneously, significantly affect timely release of laboratory results for action. Therefore, alternative methods are needed to facilitate and increase the speed of analysis, with relatively few costs. Cheap and quick methods using high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) have been reported in the literature⁹⁻¹³. However, none of the above method simultaneously determines Tramadol HCl (TMD) and paracetamol (PAR) in formulations.

Experimental

Materials, chemicals and equipment :

TMD and PAR reference standards were obtained from Yarrow Chemical Lab., Mumbai and Indoco Pvt. Ltd., Aurangabad respectively. Fixed dose combination tablets of the two compounds from ULTRACET manufacturers were bought from retail pharmacies in Aurangabad (Maharashtra). Chloroform, methanol, ethanol and ethyl acetate were obtained from Merck (India) and were of analytical grade.

A Camag HPTLC system comprising of Camag AS-30-applicator, Hamilton syringe, Camag twin trough chamber, Camag TLC Densitometer CD 60 scanner, and stationary phase pre coated with silica gel 60F₂₅₄ were used. TLC aluminum plates pre-coated with silica gel 60F₂₅₄ (20 cm × 20 cm) were from Merck. Densitometry was carried out with a Camag TLC Scanner 3 (Desaga Make) fitted with Desaga ProQuant software. Samples were applied on the TLC plates using the spray-on technique of Camag AS-30 under nitrogen gas flow, and developed in a Camag 20 cm × 20 cm twin trough chamber.

Method development and validation :

Preparation of standard solutions :

The given standard TMD 30 mg was dissolved in ethanol and made up to 10 ml in a volumetric flask. The given standard PAR 10 mg was dissolved in ethanol and made up to 10 ml in a volumetric flask, these solutions were used as working standard solutions for the analysis.

Method development :

TMD and PAR standard solutions were prepared using ethanol as solvent. The TLC plates were pre washed with methanol and activated by keeping at 115 °C for about 30 min. Solutions of 0.5 µl were applied on the TLC plates as spot bands of 5 mm using Camag AS-30. Application positions were at least 15 mm from the sides and 15 mm from the bottom of the plates. Mobile phase components were mixed prior to use and the development chamber was left to saturate with mobile phase vapour for 20 min before each run. Development of the plate was carried out by the ascending technique to a migration distance of 7 cm. Then the plates were dried on a hot plate. Room temperature and relative humidity were always maintained at 20 ± 2 °C and 55% RH ± 5 %RH, respectively.

Densitometric scanning was done in absorbance mode at 254 nm using a deuterium lamp. The slit dimensions were set at 5 mm × 0.45 mm, the scanning speed at 20 mm/s and the data resolution at 100 m/step. Single wavelength detection was performed because we are dealing with main components analyses and not impurity determinations where scanning at the individual λ_{\max} values would be preferred.

The separation conditions were based on the TLC screening test for TMD and PAR fixed-dose combination tablets described in the GPHF Minilab[®] kit²⁰. These conditions were transferred to the HPTLC system and the results were evaluated with the aim of achieving an optimum separation between spots ($R_s \geq 1.5$) and a migration of spots with R_f values between 0.2 and 0.4 in order to ensure separation reproducibility²¹ (Fig. 3).

Method validation :

Linearity of the calibration line :

A standard stock solution with 3 mg/ml and 1 mg/ml, TMD and PAR respectively, was prepared. A volume of 0.5 µl of each solution was applied on the TLC plate to deliver 1.5, 3, 6, 9, 12, 15 and 18 µl of TMD per spot and 0.5, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 and 6 µl of PAR per spot (Tables 1 and 2). This was done in triplicate and repeated for three days. For each concentration, the applied spot bands were evenly distributed across the plate to minimize possible variation along the silica layer. The linearity was evalu-

Fig. 3. Chromatogram showing resolution of Tramadol HCl ($R_f = 0.2 \pm 0.03$) and paracetamol ($R_f = 0.4 \pm 0.04$).

Table 1. Observation table for calibration curve of Tramadol HCl

Amount (μ l per spot)	Area (cm^2)
1.5	141.63
3	289.94
6	490.53
9	650.27
12	757.67
15	1030.22
18	1148.29

Fig. 4. Calibration curve of Tramadol HCl.

Table 2. Observation table for calibration curve of paracetamol

Amount (μ l per spot)	Area (cm^2)
0.5	549
1	792
2	978
3	1203
4	1452
5	1586
6	1806

Fig. 5. Calibration curve of paracetamol.

ated visually by looking at the calibration curves, of TMD and PAR in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 respectively.

Precision :

The repeatability and time-different intermediate precision were determined simultaneously. Intra-day assay precision was found by analysis of standard drug at three times on the same day. Inter-day assay precision was carried out using at three different days, and percentage relative standard deviation (%RSD) was calculated. The RSD was found to be less than 2 for both intra-day and inter-day precision. Repeatability of sample application was assessed by spotting 1 µl of drug solution, six times. From the peak areas, the percentage RSD was determined. The intra-day and inter-day accuracy and precision of TMD and PAR were shown in Tables 3 and 4 respectively. The complete validation parameters are shown in Table 7.

Accuracy :

The accuracy of the method was assessed by determination of the recovery of the method at 3 different con-

centrations (80%, 100% and 120% concentration) by addition of known amount of standard to the placebo. Solutions were prepared in triplicate and analyzed. This procedure was repeated for three consecutive days. Calibration curves to estimate the concentration of drug per spot were measured daily on the same plates as the samples. The accuracy was determined and expressed as percentage recovery (Table 5).

Analysis of tablet sample :

The method was used for quantitation of TMD and PAR in tablet samples procured from local pharmacy. For sample preparation, ethanol was used as solvent for extraction and dilution. Twenty tablets were ground into fine powder. Portions of powder equivalent to 10 mg of TMD were accurately weighed into a 10 ml volumetric flask. About 8 ml of ethanol was added and the mixture was sonicated for 10 min. The mixture was diluted to volume with ethanol, mixed well and filtered through

Table 3. Evaluation of intra-day and inter-day accuracy and precision of TMD

TMD taken (µg/ml)	Intra-day accuracy and precision			Inter-day accuracy and precision		
	TMD found (µg/ml)	RE %	RSD %	TMD found (µg/ml)	RE %	RSD %
3	3.04	2.33	1.87	3.02	2.31	1.96
6	5.99	2.75	1.12	6.11	2.87	1.72
9	9.13	1.72	1.97	9.35	1.78	1.29

RE - Relative error; RSD - Relative standard deviation.

Table 4. Evaluation of intra-day and inter-day accuracy and precision of PAR

PAR taken (mg/ml)	Intra-day accuracy and precision			Inter-day accuracy and precision		
	PAR found (µg/ml)	RE %	RSD %	PAR found (µg/ml)	RE %	RSD %
1	1.01	0.79	1.93	1.02	0.80	1.94
2	1.99	0.99	1.21	2.01	1.56	1.90
3	3.02	1.66	1.34	2.98	2.18	1.79

RE - Relative error; RSD - Relative standard deviation.

Table 5. Recovery data

Level (%)	Amount added		Amount found		% Recovery		% RSD	
	(mg)		(mg)					
	TMD	PAR	TMD	PAR	TMD	PAR	TMD	PAR
80	8	69.3	8.01	69.1	100.12	100.10	0.92	1.38
100	10	86.7	10.15	86.1	101.50	99.33	1.07	1.31
120	12	104.04	11.82	105.1	98.60	101.01	1.50	1.70

*An average value ± relative standard deviation of 5 observations.

Whatman filter paper no. 41 to obtain the sample stock solution. This solution contains 1 µg of TMD and 2.33 µg of PAR in 1 µl ethanol, used as test solution for quantitative analysis of TMD from ULTRACET tablet. 5 µl of the test solution was applied on the pre-coated silica gel 60F₂₅₄ plate. From the peak area, the amount of TMD and PAR in formulation were simultaneously calculated using the respective calibration graph. The amount obtained per tablet and percentage label claim are shown in Table 6. Chromatogram showing TMD (peak 1) and PAR

Assay results show excellent label claim of 100.8% for Tramadol HCl and 101.73% for paracetamol (Table 6). In conclusion, the method was considered to have an acceptable sensitivity, recovery, precision and accuracy (Table 7).

Conclusion :

A new, quick, precise and accurate method based on HPTLC has been developed. Assay results show excellent label claim of 100.8% for Tramadol HCl and 101.73%

Table 6. Assay results of tablet dosage form

Formulation Tablet	Actual amount (µg)		Amount found ± SD (µg)		% of Drug found ± SD	
	TMD	PAR	TMD	PAR	TMD	PAR
	5	11.5	5.04 ± 0.01	11.7	100.8 ± 1.5	101.73 ± 1.7

(peak 2) from the solution of spiked tablet matrix. Mobile phase of chloroform, methanol and ethyl acetate (7.5 : 1.5 : 0.5, v : v : v) detection at 254 nm. Chromatogram showing resolution of TMD ($R_f = 0.2 \pm 0.03$) and PAR ($R_f = 0.4 \pm 0.04$) as shown in Fig. 3.

For the determination of Tramadol HCl and paracetamol, sample solutions were prepared in triplicate and analyzed according to the method procedure. Sample and standard solutions were spotted on the same plate.

Results and discussion

During the stage of method development different mobile phases were tried and the mobile phase comprising of chloroform, methanol and ethyl acetate (7.5 : 1.5 : 0.5, v : v : v) was confirmed. A good linear relationship was obtained over the concentration range 2.5–32.5 µg/spot of Tramadol HCl (TMD) and 10–50 µg/spot for paracetamol (PAR) respectively. The linear regression data showed a regression coefficient of 0.989 for Tramadol HCl (Fig. 4) and 0.987 for paracetamol (Fig. 5). The LOD with signal/noise ratio were found to be 2.308 and 0.829 µg/spot for Tramadol HCl and paracetamol respectively. The LOQ with signal/noise ratio was found to be 6.995 ng and 2.513 µg/spot for Tramadol HCl and paracetamol respectively. The repeatability showed excellent % RSD less than 2% after six applications (Tables 3 and 4). The recovery was 100.12, 101.50 and 98.60% for Tramadol HCl and 100.10, 99.33 and 101.01% for paracetamol at 80%, 100% and 120% levels (Table 5).

Table 7. Summary of validation parameters

Parameters	Tramadol HCl	Paracetamol
Accuracy (%)	100.8% ± 1.5	101.01% ± 1.7
Intra-day precision (%RSD)	0.73	0.49
Inter-day precision (%RSD)	1.72	1.21
Sensitivity (µg/cm ²)	0.0026	0.0005
Limit of Detection (LOD µg/spot) ^a	2.3085	0.8293
Limit of Quantification (LOQ, µg/spot) ^a	6.9955	2.5131

^aBased on S.D. of response and slope of regression curve.

for paracetamol (Table 6), developed for routine analysis of Tramadol HCl and paracetamol in fixed-dose combination tablets. The method was successfully validated for linearity, precision and accuracy. It has the advantage over HPLC methods in general. It consumes less than 35 ml of mobile phase per run (18 samples per plate), whereas HPLC methods would consume not less than 100 ml per runs of similar number of samples. If we consider the time from sample preparation to densitometric evaluation for one plate, the new method takes an average of 1 h, whereas HPLC methods would generally take more than 2 h for the same number of samples. It is cheap and quick, therefore suitable for routine analysis of Tramadol HCl and paracetamol in fixed-dose combination tablets.

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